

ON THE CONSTITUTION OF NITRO- β -METHYL- UMBELLIFERONE METHYL ETHER AND OF CHLORORESORCIN.

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Pechmann and Obermiller* (*Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 666) observed that when β -methylumbelliferone methyl ether was nitrated in addition to 8-nitro-7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin (I, R=H; R'=Me; R''=NO₂), m.p. 230°, another isomeric nitro compound, probably 6-nitro-7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin (I, R=NO₂; R'=Me; R''=H), m.p. 281°, was isolated, the position of the nitro group being undetermined (*cf.* Beilstein, "Handbuch der organischen Chemie," Vierte Auflage, Band XVIII, p. 33).

It is now found that 4-nitroresorcin (Borsche, *Annalen*, 1903, **330**, 106) condenses with acetoacetic ester producing 6-nitro-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (I, R=NO₂; R'=R''=H) in presence of sulphuric acid as the condensing agent. The presence of a nitro group greatly depresses the reactivity of the resorcin molecule in coumarin formation, since no product could be isolated by reacting 4-nitroresorcin with methyl- or ethyl-acetoacetic ester. It should be observed that the nitro group in position 4 has a more depressing effect than the nitro group in position 2 (*cf.* Chakravarti and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 622).

The constitution of the nitro- β -methylumbelliferone methyl ether, m.p. 281°, has been now proved to be 6-nitro-7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin by its demethylation to 6-nitro-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, the condensation product of 4-nitroresorcin with acetoacetic ester.

The 6-nitro-7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin has been reduced to the amino derivative, the diazo solution of which on treatment with cuprous chloride in hydrochloric acid gives 6-chloro-7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin (I, R=Cl; R'=Me; R''=H),

The latter is found to be identical with the methyl ether of the condensation product of chlororesorcin with acetoacetic ester, thereby fixing the position

* The work of Pechmann and Cohen, referred to by Chakravarti and Ghosh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 792) should be the work of Pechmann and Obermiller.

(4) of the chlorine atom in chlororesorcin. This constitutes further evidence in support of the position assigned to the chlorine atom in chlororesorcin by Clark (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 319) and by Chakravarti and Ghosh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 791).

EXPERIMENTAL.

6-Nitro-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin.—A cold mixture of 4-nitroresorcin (5 g.) and acetoacetic ester (4 g.) was treated with sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84, 8 c.c.) drop by drop. The mixture was left for 2 days and then poured into ice water, the oil separating was washed with water and then with rectified spirit, when yellow crystals were obtained. These were recrystallised from glacial acetic acid (charcoal) as yellow needles, m.p. 253°. (Found: N, 6.28. $C_{10}H_7O_5N$ requires N, 6.3 per cent).

6-Chloro-7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin.—(i) 6-Chloro-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, the condensation product of 4-chlororesorcin with acetoacetic ester (Chakravarti and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 622) was methylated by dimethyl sulphate in the usual manner. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid as colourless needles, m.p. 252°. (Found: Cl, 15.6. $C_{11}H_9O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 15.8 per cent).

(ii) A solution of 6-amino-7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin (1.5 g.) (Pechmann and Obermiller, *loc. cit.*) in hot concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) was cooled in ice, when the hydrochloride separated as a fine precipitate. It was diazotised in the usual way and the diazo solution treated in the cold with a solution of cuprous chloride in hydrochloric acid. After standing for some time and subsequent heating on a water-bath for half an hour, 6-chloro-7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin separated, which was collected, washed with hydrochloric acid and water and finally crystallised from glacial acetic acid as colourless needles, m.p. 251° (mixed m.p. with the compound prepared by the first method).

Demethylation of 6-Nitro-7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin.—6-Nitro-7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin (1.5 g.) was heated with aluminium chloride (4 g.) in an oil-bath, the temperature being gradually raised to 150° during the course of 3 hours. The brown solid obtained on treating with ice was dissolved in sodium hydroxide and the solution acidified. The flocculent brown precipitate was dried and crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 253°, the m. p. being not depressed when mixed with 6-nitro-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, the condensation product of 4-nitroresorcin with acetoacetic ester.